
Befriending the Other Religions: Vatican II and the New Orientations

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Abstract: in this paper the author wants to show that Vatican II has brought about radical changes in the Church's attitude to other Christian Churches, other religions and the modern world. These changes and innovations can be clearly seen if we keep in mind the totally different attitude which prevailed in the Church before the Council. Remarkably, the Council has taken several steps to befriend the non-Catholic Christians and their Churches, the non-Christians and their religions and the modern world. It is upto the Catholic faithful now to imbibe the spirit of this great Council and establish cordial relations with non-Catholic Christians, the followers of other faiths and the modern world.

Keywords: Vatican II, The Church's Openness to Other Religions, Befriending the Other Churches, Befriending the World

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In this paper I shall contend that Vatican II has brought about radical changes in the Church's attitude to other Christian Churches, other religions and the modern world. These changes can be clearly seen if we keep in mind the totally different attitude which prevailed in the Church before the Council.

The situation of the Church during the last four hundred years (before Vatican II) was largely due to the impact of the Council of Trent. After pointing out that this Council had succeeded in stemming the tide of the Reformation that threatened to destroy Catholicism and in starting a process of Church renewal, Giuseppe Alberigo observes:

But the price paid for this successful orientation cannot be overlooked; it can be summed up as a drastic isolation of Roman Christianity, now cut off and insulated from any interaction with the other Christian traditions of East and West, condemned to an attitude of defensiveness toward the modern world and, finally, surrounded by a *cordon sanitaire* to prevent contamination from alien cultures. Never in the history of Christianity had the *massa damnata* been made to include so much and so many; never had Christianity so extended and exacerbated its own estrangement from the fortunes of the human race (Alberigo, 1987: 13-14).

The Council of Trent had an enormous impact on the Church for about four centuries. During this period the Church's isolation from the other Christian Churches grew. The struggle with the Protestant Reformation and the opposition to modern culture led to the development of "the 'closed' ecclesiology of the post-tridentine period in which the Church is a fortified castle, jealous of its purity and bristling with condemnations" (Alberigo, 1987: 13-14). There was a strong resistance to all attempts break out of this fortress mentality and open up lines of communication with various cultures or to build bridges between the Church and the common human condition. The French Revolution and Vatican I only aggravated the situation. "Ecclesiocentrism thus reached levels that were new in relation to the entire Christian tradition" (Alberigo, 1987: 15).

Looking back on the Council and carefully examining its documents one can clearly see that its basic thrust was the Church's recovery of the integral Christian tradition and the establishment of cordial relations with the other Christian Churches, the diverse religions and cultures of humanity and the modern world.

1. Befriending the Other Churches

From Anathema to Acceptances

From the beginning of Christianity divisions began to take place in the Church. These divisions led to the emergence of different Churches. By the middle of the 5th century all the churches other than the Greco-Roman Church were shut out of the Catholic Church. In the 11th century the Greek Church got separated from the Roman Church. In the 16th century the Roman Church itself was split. As a result of the Reformation several Churches came into existence – Lutheran Churches, Reformed Churches of Calvin, Zwingli and so on.

The reasons for division in the Church were many and varied. First of all, there were theological reasons. Sometimes doctrinal differences paved the way for the emergence of new churches. Disciplinary matters too caused division. But there is reason to believe that social and cultural factors also caused division in the Church. This was quite evident in the separation between the Greek Church and the Roman Church. Diversity of culture may have played a role in Luther's revolt against Rome – the Germanic culture against the Latin culture. As Christopher Dawson has observed: "Most of the great schisms and heresies in the history of the Christian church have their roots in social and national antipathies, and if this had been clearly recognized by the theologians the history of Christianity would have been a very different one" (Dawson, 2002: 32). Joseph Neuner calls attention to another factor: "Luther's revolt is not primarily a theological challenge of traditional doctrines but a revolution

against the domination of the Christian people through the clergy in a spirit totally alien to Jesus Christ” (Neuner, 1983: 13).

The way the Catholic Church reacted to the members of these Churches were also alien to the spirit of Jesus Christ. They were condemned quite harshly. In the Church there developed a feeling of animosity towards the members of these Churches. They were anathema to the authorities of the Catholic Church.

Befriending Non-Catholics

All this changed with Vatican II. The Council sought to befriend non-Catholic Christians and their churches. It admitted that the divisions in the Church were caused both by the Catholics as well as non-Catholic Christians and hence “both sides were to blame” (UR 3). In unmistakable terms Vatican II declared:

However one cannot impute the sin of separation to those who at present are born into these Communities and are instilled therein with Christ’s faith. The Catholic Church accepts them with respect and affection as brothers and sisters. For men and women who believe in Christ and have been properly baptized are brought into a certain, though imperfect, communion with the Catholic Church. Undoubtedly the differences that exist in varying degrees between them and the Catholic Church – whether in doctrine and sometimes in discipline, or concerning the structure of the Church – do indeed create many and sometimes serious obstacles to full ecclesiastical communion. These the ecumenical movement is striving to overcome. Nevertheless, all those justified by faith through baptism are incorporated into Christ. They therefore have a right to be honoured by the title of Christian and are properly regarded as brothers and sisters in the Lord by the sons and daughters of the Catholic Church (UR 3).

In this text two statements are quite significant: (1) The Catholic Church accepts the members of these Churches with respect and affection; (2) They are properly regarded as brothers and sisters by the children of the Catholic Church.

This was the first step in the process of befriending non-Catholic Christians. The second step was to recognize the non-Catholic Christian communities as Churches. In an earlier draft of the Dogmatic Constitution on the Church there was a statement which totally identified the Church of Christ with the Roman Catholic Church.” The Church of Christ *is* the Roman Catholic Church” (LG 8). This was based on the teaching of Pope Pius XII that the Church of Christ, the Roman Catholic Church and the Mystical Body of Christ are one and the same thing (Neuner & Dupuis, 2008: 847, 858). The Council changed this statement to: “The Church of Christ *subsists* in the Roman Catholic” (LG 8). It then observed that “many elements of sanctification and of truth can be found outside of her visible structure” (LG 8). Whatever be the exact meaning of this changed formulation, it does imply that the Catholic Church does not exhaust the ecclesial possibilities of the Church of Christ. These ecclesial possibilities are realized in the other Churches. Hence the Council calls them Christian Churches (LG 15, UR 3).

These Christian Churches have many elements in common with the Catholic Church: Sacred Scripture, faith in the Triune God and Jesus Christ the Saviour. They celebrate baptism and some of the other sacraments. Many of them have the episcopate and venerate the Blessed Virgin Mary.

The Council took a third step when it declared that these Churches have significance in the mystery of salvation. The Spirit of Christ uses them as means of salvation for their members (UR 3).

In its effort to befriend the other Churches, the Council took two more steps. While speaking about dialogue within and without the Church, Vatican II states: “Our hearts embrace also those brothers and communities not yet living with us in full communion” (GS 92). The Council also expresses its desire to collaborate with the members of the other Churches:

Cooperation among all Christians vividly expresses that bond which already unites them, and it sets in clearer relief the features of Christ the Servant. Such cooperation, which has already begun in many countries, should be ever increasingly developed, particularly in regions where a social and technical evolution is taking place. It should contribute to a just appreciation of the dignity of the human person, the promotion of the blessings of peace, the application of gospel principles to social life, and the advancement of the arts and sciences in a Christian spirit (UR 12).

Such collaboration is to be extended to the fight against social evils like poverty and illiteracy. The Council goes on to add: “Through such cooperation, all believers in Christ are able to learn easily how they can understand each other better and esteem each other more, and how the road to the unity of Christian may be made smooth” (UR 12).

2. Befriending the Other Religions

Old Understanding of Religions

For centuries most Christians believed that Christianity was the only true religion since it alone was divinely instituted. Perhaps the best known exponent of this view was Dr. Henrik Kraemer of Netherlands, who, in 1938, published a book titled: *The Christian Message in a Non-Christian World* (Kraemer 1938). “The main thesis of my book”, he wrote in the Foreword, “is that the Christian Revelation is ... absolutely *sui generis* (Kraemer 1938: ix). Following Barth and Kierkegaard, Kraemer maintained that there is an ‘absolute qualitative difference’ between the Gospel of Christ and all other religions. “When Christianity as a total religious system approaches the non-Christian religions as total religious systems, there is only difference and antithesis” (Kraemer 1938: 131-132 & 115-120). Hence it is not possible to compare Christianity with any other religion. “There is no point of contact: ... there are no bridges from human religious consciousness to Christ” (Kraemer 1938:

131-132). Moreover non-Christian religions are, according to this view, quite incapable of leading human beings to a true knowledge of God or of salvation.

And among Catholics a Church-centred ecclesiology held sway for a long period of time. According to this theology the Church was the only God-appointed means of salvation. There was no salvation outside the Church (Neuner & Dupuis, 2008: 810). The Church possessed the fullness of truth and can teach it infallibly. She was the only authoritative interpreter of the natural Law. By and large the Church's attitude to the other religions was quite negative. It was unthinkable that these religions might be ways of salvation for their followers. In 1867 Pius IX rejected as errors the following:

Everyone is free to embrace and profess the religion which by the light of reason he judges to be true. Men can find the way to eternal salvation and attain eternal salvation by the practice of any religion whatever (Neuner & Dupuis, 2008: 810).

No wonder, then, that Catholic missionaries were not interested in dialogue and collaboration with the followers of other religions. Speaking of them E. C. Dewick has remarked:

They went out with love for non-Christians in their hearts, but not with any thought of appreciating the non-Christian religions. Their purpose was simply to rescue souls from the clutches of heathenism in this world and from the fires of hell in the next. They went to give, and not to receive; to save, not to cooperate (Dewick, 1953: 116).

In all fairness it must be admitted that there were some Catholic thinkers like Cardinal Nicholas of Cusa who adopted a positive approach to the non-Christian religions. But they were not representative of the position generally held by Catholics.

Positive Understanding of Religions

It is in Vatican II that an Ecumenical Council for the first time dealt with the non-Christian religions. While discussing the schema on the Church the Council Fathers requested that non-Christians be treated not globally but according to the religious groups to which they belonged. Hence *Lumen Gentium* deals with the Jews, the Muslims, those who believe in God and then the non-believers (LG 16). *Nostra Aetate* speaks of Hinduism, Buddhism, Islam and Judaism (NA). And Vatican II vindicates religious freedom not only for Christians but also for the followers of other religions (DH 4). Thus recognition is accorded to the world religions.

This is the first step in the Council's effort to befriend the other religions.

The second step is the expression of genuine appreciation of the positive values to be found in these religions – truth and goodness, grace and holiness (LG 16; NA 2; OT 16). Vatican II believes that God is the source of these values. According to the Dogmatic Constitution on the Church, “whatever goodness or truth is found among them is looked upon by the Church ... as given by Him who enlightens all men and women that they may finally have life” (LG 16). Here the text refers to John 1:9 which says that the Word was the true light which enlightens everyone. John is here speaking of the eternal Word and not the incarnate Word. The Decree on the Missionary Activity of the Church regards whatever truth and grace are to be found among the nations “as a secret presence of God” (AG 9).

Hence for the Council these religions are not pure human creations. God is at work in their origin and growth.

This leads to the third step. Vatican II exhorts the children of the Church:

Prudently and lovingly, through dialogue and collaboration with the followers of other religions, and in witness of Christian faith and life, acknowledge, preserve, and promote

the spiritual and moral goods found among these men, as well as the values in their society and culture (NA 3).

The Council looks upon dialogue as a means to arrive at truth through love and as a spiritual pursuit:

We also turn our thoughts to all who acknowledge God and who preserve in their traditions precious elements of religion and humanity. We want frank conversation to compel us all to receive the inspirations of the Spirit faithfully and to measure up to them energetically.

For our part, the desire for such dialogue which can lead to truth through love alone, excludes no one, though an appropriate measure of prudence must undoubtedly be exercised (GS 92).

The Council also encourages collaboration among the followers of different religions:

Since God the Father is the origin and purpose of all men and women, we are all called to be brothers and sisters. Therefore, if we have been summoned to the same destiny, which is both human and divine, we can and we should work together without violence and deceit in order to build up the world in genuine peace (GS 92).

Thus Vatican II looks upon the followers of other religions as partners in our common quest for justice and peace in the world.

3. Befriending the Modern World

Moving Away from the Middle Ages

Right from the beginning the Church's attitude to the world was ambiguous (Neuner, 1981: 449). On the one hand it looked upon the world as an object of God's love, since God created it and continued to care for it. On the other hand it regarded the world as hostile to God, since it had closed itself against God in its sinful self-sufficiency. Both John and Paul, among the New Testament writers, gave expression to this ambiguity (McKenzie, 1994: 942-944). During the centuries of Roman persecution the

Church adopted a very negative attitude to the world. It thought of itself as a community of believers surrounded by a wicked world (Neuner, 1981: 448). Baptism was the moment of decision when a person renounced the spirit of the world and embraced the spirit of Christ (Schillebeeckx, 1981: 56). The Didache has preserved a text which shows that the Eucharistic celebration concluded with the words: “Let grace come, let this world pass away (Kleist, 1988 10:6).

The Church of the Middle ages was somewhat ambivalent in its approach to the world. It fostered a spirituality based on a contempt of the world. As Alfons Auer had pointed out:

The basic attitude of the Middle Ages was one-sidedly that of flight from the world. The monastic ascetical ideal prevailed also in the world; medieval Christianity was predominantly shaped by monks. Its ideal of life had a fascinating effect also upon laymen; one thought he could serve God best and most uncompromisingly when he bade farewell to the world (Auer, 1965: 6).

There was on the other hand an effort made to subjugate the world to the Church or even to absorb it. To quote Auer once again,

In the greatness of the Middle Ages its very limitations become all the more apparent. No other age was able to achieve to the same degree a blending of the terrestrial and heavenly kingdom into a single universal order in which the temporal realms were directly ordered to the spiritual reality of the Church, and even – in order to maintain this order – directly or at least indirectly subjugated to ecclesiastical regulation. This unitary order necessarily resulted in a situation in which temporal matters were not adequately considered with respect to their inherent value nor sufficiently seen as fashioned according to their own laws. In the long run, the sacred order of the Middle Ages amounted to the same thing as Monophysitism (Auer, 1965: 8-9).

In a way the modern phenomenon of secularization is a reaction to this tendency on the part of the Church to absorb the world and not to respect it in its otherness. Gradually human beings, human society and its institutions, the arts and the sciences, work and professions began to assert their autonomy with respect to the Church and to affirm their intrinsic value. However, the Church reacted to this process quite negatively. As Avery Dulles observes,

The papal encyclicals from Gregory XVI (1831-46) to Pius XII (1939-59) continually deplore modern errors. *The Syllabus of Errors*, published by Pius IX in 1864, comes to a climax with Error No. 80: “The Roman pontiff can and should reconcile himself with, and adjust to progress, liberalism, and recent civilization.” In 1907 the Church condemned Modernism, a movement that had begun as an effort by Catholics to bring the Church abreast of the times. Much later, just as World War II was breaking out, Pius XII issued his first encyclical, *Darkness over the Earth* (*Summi Pontificatus*, Oct. 20, 1939), reflecting remnants of this antimodernist mentality (Dulles, 1974: 31).

Positive Attitude to the World

Pope John XXIII had quite a different attitude. In his Apostolic Constitution convoking Vatican II he emphatically declared: “Distrustful souls see only darkness burdening the face of the earth. We, instead, like to reaffirm all our confidence in our Saviour, who has not left the world he redeemed” (John XIII, 1991: 704). And in his opening address to the first session he made it clear that he was not one of those who “in these modern times... can see nothing but prevarication and ruin” (John XVIII, 1061: 712). Pope John’s positive attitude to the modern world has had a great impact on *Gaudium et Spes*. That is probably why it has turned out to be one of the most inspiring documents of the Council.

Right at the beginning the Pastoral Constitution explains how it understands the modern world:

Therefore, the Council focuses its attention on the world of men, the whole human family along with the sum of those realities in the midst of which that family lives. It gazes upon that world which is the theatre of man's history, and carries the marks of his energies, his tragedies, and his triumphs; that world which the Christian sees as created and sustained by its Maker's love, fallen indeed into the bondage of sin, yet emancipated now by Christ (GS 2).

There are three important elements in the Council's understanding of the modern world. This world is a world of human beings together with the subhuman creation in the midst of which they live. It is the scene of their history and bears the mark of their labour and their struggle, their successes and their failures. Though this world fell into sin it has been liberated by Christ. This is a very positive way of looking at the world. It is interesting to note that Vatican II regards the difficulties brought about by the rapid changes taking place in the world as a 'crisis of growth' (GS 4).

All this constitutes the first step in the Council's befriending of the modern world.

The second step is that Vatican II has adopted a positive attitude to the process of secularization. In unmistakable terms it declares:

If by the autonomy of earthly affairs we mean that created things and societies themselves enjoy their own laws and values which must be gradually deciphered, put to use, and regulated by men, then it is entirely right to demand that autonomy. Such is not merely required by modern man, but harmonizes also with the will of the Creator. For by the very circumstance of their having been created, all things are endowed with their own stability, truth, goodness, proper laws, and order. Man must respect these as he isolates them by the appropriate methods of the individual sciences or arts (GS 36).

Such a view leads to the recognition of the freedom and legitimacy of the arts and the sciences. As *Gaudium et Spes* puts it,

The Church is not against the use by human arts and sciences of their own principles and methods in their respective fields; therefore it acknowledges this lawful freedom and affirms the legitimate autonomy of culture and especially of the sciences (GS 59).

The third step that the Council has taken in befriending the modern world is this: It expresses its appreciation of the developments in the world:

The Council, therefore, looks with great respect upon all the true, good, and just elements found in the very wide variety of institutions which the human race has established for itself and constantly continues to establish (GS 42).

Vatican II goes on to add:

The Church further recognizes that worthy elements are found in today's social movements, especially an evolution toward unity, a process of wholesome socialization and of association in civic and economic realms. For the promotion of unity belongs to the innermost nature of the Church, since she is, "by her relationship with Christ, both a sacramental sign and an instrument of intimate union with God, and of the unity of all humankind" (GS 42).

A fourth step is the manifestation of the Council's eagerness to dialogue with the modern world. It believes that "this Council can provide no more eloquent proof of its solidarity with the entire human family with which it is bound up, as well as its respect and love for that family, than by engaging with it in conversation about these various problems" (GS 3).

In this context I would like to quote a pertinent observation made by Avery Dulles:

The Pastoral Constitution, in particular, sought to bring the

Church into dialogue with the world on a basis of mutual respect and reciprocal give-and-take... The Council sees the Church as involved with the world in the tremendous social and cultural transformations of our times, and affirms the Church's solidarity with 'the joys and the hopes, the griefs and the anxieties of the men and women of this age'. Renouncing any attitude of haughty superiority, the Council expresses 'great respect' for "all the true, good and just elements found in the very wide variety of institutions which the human race has established for itself and constantly continues to establish". The Church here professes its readiness to put its talents and resources to work in order to contribute to secular goals such as peace, freedom, justice and human dignity (Dulles, 1971: 11).

What is perhaps most significant in the Pastoral Constitution is that it conceives the role of the Church in the modern world as that of a servant. Inspired by no earthly ambition, the Church wishes only to carry forward the work of Christ who came not to be served but to serve (GS 3). Hence "Christians cannot yearn for anything more ardently than to serve the men and women of the modern world ever more generously and effectively" (GS 93). The document spells out concretely the kind of service that the Church can render to human persons, human communities and human activity in the world (GS 40-43).

Yet another step in the Council's befriending of the modern world is this: It gratefully acknowledges the benefits the Church has received from the world. Vatican II has stated:

Thanks to the experience of past ages, the progress of the sciences, and the treasures hidden in the various forms of human culture, the nature of man himself is more clearly revealed and new roads to truth are opened. These benefits profit the Church, too (GS 44).

The Council goes on to add:

Since the Church has a visible and social structure as a sign of her unity in Christ, she can and ought to be enriched by the

development of human social life. The reason is not that the constitution given her by Christ is defective, but so that she may understand it more penetratingly, express it better, and adjust it more successfully to our times (GS 44).

Conclusion

To conclude: The Second Vatican Council has taken several steps to befriend the non-Catholic Christians and their Churches, the non-Christians and their religions and the modern world. It is up to the Catholic faithful now to imbibe the spirit of this great Council and establish cordial relations with non-Catholic Christians, the followers of other faiths and the modern world.

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Notes

1. Speaking of the members of the other churches the authorities of the Catholic Church use expressions like “perverse opinions and errors”, “extraordinary boldness”, “arrogant claim” etc. See Neuner and Dupuis. 2008: 816.

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